

Reproduction of 'Zero-Shot Recommendation as Language Modeling'

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This report evaluates the reproducibility of the experimental setup and results of *Zero-Shot Recommendation as Language Modeling* [4]. We analyze whether the original paper's findings hold under independent replication and assess the robustness of its methodology. In structuring our study, we took inspiration from previous reproducibility efforts [1, 2, 5], which serve as excellent examples of how to document and evaluate replication studies effectively.

Methodology – The code used by the authors is publicly available on Google Colab and provides a good starting point for replications, although it is incomplete and requires many adjustments. Thanks to these changes, we were able to carry out the experiment.

Results – We successfully ran the code and obtained results for 4 of 5 methods, reproducing the core results, even if we faced several numerical deviations and problems with the last method.

What was easy - The paper is clear and well structured. The code is available and pre-trained models are used.

What was difficult - the public code contains no documentation and some essential elements to enable the reproducibility of some results are missing. Another significant constraint is the computational requirement needed to reproduce the original experiments.

Communication with original authors - We contacted the authors by email to request clarification of some calculations performed in the original paper and how to manage the results in the Weight and Biases framework. We received a response that partially answered our questions.

CCS Concepts: • **Information systems** → **Recommender systems**; • **Computing methodologies** → *Natural language processing*; *Reproducibility*; *Experimental design*.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Reproducibility, Experimental Design, Statistical Significance, Recommendation Systems, Language Modeling

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1 INTRODUCTION

The paper looks at a new approach to recommendation systems using off-the-shelf pre-trained language models, which makes recommendations in a zero-shot setting. 'Zero-shot' means that the model is not specifically trained for recommendations tasks, but uses its existing knowledge. Being able to use these models would facilitate addressing this kind of task, since they don't require structured training data.

The main claims of the paper can be summarized as follows:

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- Pretrained language models (LM) can be used to perform movie recommendations without being adapted to this specific task;
- The corpus analysis showed that that prompt design affects the results but is not essential to achieve good results;
- Increasing the number of ratings per user makes the performances worse and decreases the stability;
- The proposed method significantly outperforms BERT-NSP, while it has better results than matrix factorization only with few users (<50 for BASE and <100 for MEDIUM GPT-2);
- LM-based model can also be used for text generation but it's not always reliable.

Our goal is to verify all the claims and to do so it is necessary to reproduce the experiment and analyze the results. The workflow that we followed is described in the following sections.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The MovieLens 1M Dataset contains 1 million ratings from 6040 users for 3090 movies. The rating ranges from 0.5 to 5 and is divided into two categories: positive ratings (≥ 4) and negative ratings (≤ 2.5). Furthermore, the experiment is conducted on users with at least 21 positive and 4 negative ratings. For each user one positively (ground truth) and four negatively rated movies (distractors) are selected and the goal is to rank them ensuring that the first one is at the top. The authors also standardize the movie titles deleting the years and adjusting the articles. The evaluation metric used is MAP@1 (mean average precision at rank 1), that quantifies how often the positive movie is ranked as first, averaged across all test users.

The models used are the following:

- **GPT-2**: It is pre-trained on the WebTex corpus (the parameters are optimized for the next word prediction likelihood maximization over sequences sampled from a corpus). There are different versions of GPT models: base, medium and large, characterized by different size and thus different number of parameters.
- **BERT**: This model is pre-trained too, but with contiguous sentence prediction task. It can also be used for recommendation.
- **Bayesian Personalized Ranking (BPR)**: This algorithm is specific for recommendation problems. It maps users and items to latent factors and their dot product is used as a relevance score trained with ranking loss. The hyper-parameters used are fixed and specified in the paper.

The code used by the authors is publicly available on Google Colab, but unfortunately, we experienced several problems when we attempted to run it. It provides a good starting point for the replications, but due to its incompleteness and minimal documentation, it requires modifications and extensions. The main problem is that no code is provided to reproduce the visualizations of the original paper and neither for the different experimental set-ups. Thus, the code defines a general structure but needs to be integrated to be able to obtain results for all the models and the various combinations of variables.

2.1 Implementation Details

The code was last maintained in 2021 so we ran into several issues due to version inconsistencies, missing imports, incomplete installations and dependencies conflicts. To address this and create a more robust experimental setting, we explicitly specified them. Many necessary packages are not included in default Python setting so we had to import them manually (xpflow, bigbench, tensorflow, pandas, numpy, torch, scikit-learn, easydict, tqdm, wandb, wget, appdirs, bigbench). Moreover, the BIG-bench benchmark is used, but it is necessary to install it directly from the official repository

to ensure compatibility, get the latest version and get access to all necessary modules. We also added few dependencies (GPUUtil and dropbox) and fixed the version of datasets library.

After facing dependencies conflicts, we went through a couple of errors and code bugs. The authors used the pivot command to transform the dataset into a user-item matrix, even though it is not able to deal with duplicate values. We approached this problem replacing it with pivottable(), which allows duplicate pairs. Furthermore, in the original implementation each experiment was assigned to a unique identifier in order to avoid redundancy, checking if it already existed in a Dropbox folder before running it. However, the code fails due to authentication errors. To ensure smooth replication of the paper we removed this check. This should note have a big impact on the validity of the results as running an experiment multiple times doesn't introduce inconsistencies.

A bigger problem was the absence of a fixed seed, as it made impossible to reproduce exactly the results presented in the paper, even with the same code and dataset. Note that the user seed is fixed in the code but this is not enough, since it is not applied to all the random operations in our code. This makes it difficult to determine if observed differences are due to random fluctuations and can lead to misleading conclusions. We addressed this issue fixing the seed: this ensures to have more deterministic, robust, significant and comparable results than in the paper. The authors also didn't specify the number of runs (how many times each experiment was reproduced), even though this is essential for both replication and statistical significance.

To verify the claims, we had to extend and integrate the code, since the different experimental setups weren't already implemented. Evaluating claim 2 requires making predictions using different types of prompts, identified by the authors by a previous corpus analysis. To do it the number of movies per user sampled in the input prompt is fixed to 5. For claim 3, we need to confirm the impact of the number of ratings per user. To do so we tried different values from 0 to 20, fixing all the other factors and with the selected prompt <m1,m2,...m>. For claim 4, we compared the GPT-2 method with BERT and BPR to see their differences. Like GPT, BERT is already pre-trained and has different implementations (according to the model size/number of parameters), while matrix factorization needs to be trained and the performances change based on the number of training data. For the last one, we generated some text and checked if the recommended movies made sense or not based on our knowledge and understanding of the context.

The authors' implementation included the use of the platform WeightsandBiases, but since it makes the reproduction procedure harder (it is necessary to export the results from the wandb page) and there is no explanation on how to handle it, we decided just to store the results in data frames and use these for visualizations. Our implementation is available on Google Colab [3].

3 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In this section we present the original vs. reproduced plots.

The reproduced results for the prompt types differ from the original ones, as shown in Fig. 1 and 2: first of all, the authors presented the results only for 4 types of prompts, while we considered all the 6 types mentioned in the code. Moreover, the achieved MAP@1 values differ slightly and, in general, have higher variability.

The second plot, Fig. 3 and 4, also presents some differences: the overall trend is quite similar but our results present higher variability.

The behaviors of the 2 sizes of GPT and BERT are similar to the one in the original paper (Fig. 5 and 6). We weren't able to reproduce the results for the BPR, due to missing code and computational costs.

For the last claim (Fig. 7), we can confirm the authors' conclusion: a post-processing is needed to see if the recommendations are actually reasonable.

Fig. 1. A bar chart of the original MAP@1 values for different prompt types in the GPT model.

Fig. 2. A bar chart of the reproduced MAP@1 values for different prompt types in the GPT model.

Fig. 3. Original MAP@1 values and confidence interval for different number of movies per user.

Fig. 4. Reproduced MAP@1 values and confidence interval for different number of movies per user.

Prompt: ['Babe', 'It Takes Two', 'Nobody Loves Me', 'Love & Human Remains', 'Before Sunrise']
 Completion: ['Dracula', 'The Silence of the Lambs', 'Back to the Future', 'Buffy the Vampire Slayer', "Breakfast at Tiffany's"]

Fig. 7. Asking for recommendations

3.1 Statistical Significance

We performed a two-way ANOVA (without interaction) to check if the type of prompt and the set used in the experiment has a significant impact on the performances. On the one hand, we showed that different prompts have no significant effect (the pvalue is higher than any significance level typically chosen), whether the set used affects the performance (this confirms the high variability in the results). We are now able to confirm the authors' claim according to which the type of prompt is important but not crucial. Furthermore, we did the same with the number of movies per user used in the training part: this variable significantly affects the results.

Fig. 5. Original MAP@1 values for different model sizes.

Fig. 6. Reproduced MAP@1 values for different model sizes.

Factor	Sum Sq	df	F	p-value
prompt_id	0.020	5	1.081	0.409
Set	0.040	3	3.513	0.041

Table 1. ANOVA Results for Prompt type and Set

Factor	Sum Sq	df	F	p-value
nb_pos	0.024	7	0.778	0.613
Set	0.014	3	1.073	0.382

Table 2. ANOVA Results for number of users and Set

We were unable to run more statistical tests, such as the t-test, to see if our reproduced results and the original ones significantly differ (t-test), since the authors presented the results only through visualizations, without actually providing the numerical values. This highlights the need to make data available in future researches, to enable reproducibility and transparency.

4 DISCUSSION

The main discrepancies are probably due to our computational limits and the absence of a fixed seed. From our results it seems that the prompt has higher impact on the performances than in the original paper.

4.1 What was easy

The original paper is clear, understandable, well-written and well-structured. There is a clear overview of the claims, which simplifies the reproduction and help to proceed in an organized way. The availability of the code speeds up the process and helps understanding the methodology and the various assumptions made by the authors. The use of pre-trained models helps reducing the computational costs, even though they are still very high. Finally, even without a powerful background in the methods used and in recommendation systems, we are able to understand the workflow and the main results presented.

4.2 What was difficult

Deficient documentation — Using the authors' code was more difficult than expected due to its minimal documentation. Furthermore, there is no correspondence between the variables named in the paper and the ones in the code (e.g. in the paper they refer to 'Number of Ratings Per Test User' and 'Users in training set' for the novel losses, while the code base uses 'nb_pos' and 'offset', respectively). Additionally, there wasn't any explanation on how to handle the Weights and Biases page, interpret and extrapolate the results.

Incomplete code base – The code lacks essential elements to reproducing some experiments. Especially, there is no code for the visualizations and no code for the different experimental setup. We tried to recreate the experiments but had to make some assumptions (e.g. the number of runs/seed) that may be responsible for the differences in results.

Imprecise Results – The results are provided only via visualizations, which makes them less precise and makes the comparison with ours more difficult.

Computational restraints – A significant constraint in reproducing the paper is the computational time required to reproduce the authors' original experiments.

Visualization – The code used by the authors for the visualizations presented in the paper was not included in the Google Colab page, so we had to implement it to enable the reproducibility and make comparisons.

No seed - The missing seed makes it impossible to reproduce exactly the results due to the random nature of the operations.

5 CONCLUSION

We were able to achieve the main goal of this research, that was to reproduce the experiment, but we encountered some discrepancies from the original results. Nevertheless, we confirm the major finding of the paper: GPT-2 can actually be used for recommendation tasks without any adjustment. A possible improvement would be to conduct more experiments. Indeed, we were forced to replicate the experiment a feasible number of times for our computational resources, but a higher one would definitely increase the level of confidence and robustness in the results. As already underlined in the original paper, further research could explore ways to adjust LM for recommendation purposes or to combine LM with matrix factorization into hybrid systems.

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